

How Pleasantness Responses Depend on Tactile Stimuli Parameters

Nicole D'Aurizio
DIISM
University of Siena
Siena, Italy
nicole.daurizio2@unisi.it

Tommaso Lisini Baldi
DIISM
University of Siena
Siena, Italy
tommaso.lisini@unisi.it

Teresa Ramundo
Molecular Mind Lab.
IMT School
Lucca, Italy
teresa.ramundo@imtlucca.it

Alessandro Moscatelli
Dept. of Systems Medicine
University of Rome Tor Vergata
Roma, Italy
alessandro.moscatelli@uniroma2.it

Domenico Prattichizzo
DIISM
University of Siena
Siena, Italy
domenico.prattichizzo@unisi.it

Abstract—Haptic technology holds great potential in effectively conveying emotions in remote communications. When it comes to developing wearable haptic interfaces, there is a clear desire to simplify haptic feedback while preserving the informative content of the stimulus. This approach aims to create affective haptic devices with reduced technological complexity, as well as decrease the amount of data required for transmission in remote haptic interactions. By achieving this, the overall efficiency and practicality of haptic communication through wearable interfaces can be improved.

In this study, our focus was to examine the relationship between various parameters that govern caress-like stimulation and the subjective perception of pleasantness. Our findings revealed a slight variation in pleasantness ratings between caresses administered through linear movements and those delivered as discrete sequences of taps. The presence of vibration had little effect on the perceived pleasantness. Additionally, we discovered that the temperature and velocity of the stimulus need to be adjusted at different values for the two types of caresses (linear movements and discrete sequences of taps), indicating that the optimal settings for temperature and velocity depend on the specific type of stimulation employed.

I. THE STUDY

Haptics plays a central role for communicating and understanding the emotional state of other people in social, affective, and intimate relationships [1]. When the communication is mediated by haptic technology, the ability to truthfully convey the emotional aspects of social and affective touch is critical for enhancing the feeling of presence.

Among the haptic sensations that can be delivered in the context of mediated affective touch, caress-like stimuli have received a considerable attention. From a sociological point of view, of all emotional social signals a caress from another person is one of the most powerful interactions [2]. Slow motion stimuli like a caress recruit a special class of unmyelinated

The research leading to these results has received funding from Progetto PRIN 2017 “TIGHT: Tactile InteGration for Humans and arTificial systems”, prot. 2017SB48FP and was partially supported by the Italian Ministry of Health (Ricerca Corrente, IRCCS Fondazione Santa Lucia).

Fig. 1: The participant is tuning the temperature of the end-effector while his right forearm is stimulated. To avoid biases in the stimuli evaluation, the participant wears a headset providing white noise, and the cardboard panel prevents him from seeing his forearm during the stimulation.

sensory fibers known as C-tactile afferents (CTs), that are possibly conveying information to the insular cortex along the spinothalamic tract [3]. CT fibers innervate the hairy skin, and their conduction velocity varies between 0.6 and 1.3 m/s, i.e. about 50 times slower than the $A\beta$ myelinated afferents responsible for discriminative and sensorimotor functions of touch [3]. CTs respond to different tactile stimulations, but they are vigorously activated by gentle stroking touch characterized by very low indentation forces in the range 0.3–2.5 mN [4] at typical skin temperature [5]. These functional properties of CT afferents are in accordance with the hypothesis that the CT system represents a “second touch system” with a specific affective-emotional role [6], [7]. Based on all these evidences, several studies have sought to find the stimulation that best simulates the human caress and evokes the same pleasant sensation. Several stimuli that differed for the used tools, the velocity of the stimulation, the type of tapping [8],

the level of force [9], the temperatures [5], and the association with visual stimuli [10] were tested.

In parallel with these results, various technological devices have been developed for the purpose of creating portable systems to stimulate affective touch. These include a scarf [11], a vest [12], a jacket [13], and a sleeve [14]. In [15], the authors examined the affective response to vibrations for a hand held device.

To create a stroking sensation, a variety of actuation techniques have been used. The most widespread consists in directly stimulating the skin using lateral motion [16]–[19]. However, stroke length is limited in these direct stimulation devices, typically from 1 mm to 2 cm. Moreover, as recently reported by Nunez et al in [20], generating long stroking sensations using lateral stimulation require complex actuation and mechanical design which would likely result in a heavy and bulky device. As an alternative, one research group created a stroking sensation using an air jet [21]. Similarly, this is difficult to implement into a wearable device because it requires access to compressed air.

These limitations have led researchers to create the illusion of motion across the skin using devices equipped with multiple actuators placed in fixed positions on the arm and activated sequentially, rather than relying on a single moving actuator. Numerous studies have explored the use of vibration [22], [23], investigating its potential in generating stroking sensations [15], [24], [25]. In fact, to generate vibrotactile sensations is by far the simplest and most used method of providing haptic feedback in wearable devices [26], mainly because of the ubiquity of actuators and their ease of integration into devices. Huisman and colleagues used an array of 4 vibratory motors on the ventral side of the participant’s lower arm to stimulate a stroking sensation [24]. A similar device was created by Israr and colleagues using 6 voice coil vibrotactile factors on the participant’s forearm [25]. In both experiments, the stimulation was rated as pleasant and similar to a caress. Recent studies have demonstrated the generation of a stroking sensation on the arm using only normal force [27]. An example of wearable device able to perform skin indentation to simulate a stroking sensation using a matrix of linear actuators is in [28].

These studies open the possibility of developing wearable devices able to convey emotions or feelings of closeness at a distance through the sense of touch exploiting a simplified set of stimuli. However, to the best of our knowledge, the interaction between tapping, vibrations, velocity, and temperature in this kind of stimuli has not been investigated yet. Thus, in this work we propose a careful comparison of different haptic stimuli to identify the best combination for generating a pleasant, caress-like sensation.

II. METHODS

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup consisted of an Omega.3 haptic device (Force Dimension, CH) with a custom end-effector (see Fig. 2a). The Omega.3 has a delta-based parallel kinematics structure with active gravity compensation providing up to

Fig. 2: The haptic interface adopted to stimulate the participants’ forearm. In a), the Omega.3 haptic device with a custom end-effector. In b), the exploded view of the terminal part of the end-effector detailing all the embedded components: a 3D printed support (A), the temperature sensor (B), two fans (C), the heat sink (D), and the Peltier Cell (E). In c), the assembled view of the terminal part of the end-effector.

12 N 3D active force, and a positioning resolution less than 0.01 mm. The haptic interface can be actuated by controlling position, velocity, and applied force of the end effector thanks to the Force Dimension SDK.

The end-effector was ad-hoc designed for the purpose of this work, and 3D printed in ABS. The rendered images are reported in Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c. The structure embeds two different actuators, i.e. a voice coil (vibro-transducer Vp210, operational frequency range of 20-15000 Hz, Acouve Laboratory, Inc., JP) and a Peltier TEC module (ET-007-10-15, 8 x 8 x 3.8 mm, Adaptive, UK), three heatsinks (BGA-STD-015, 14 x 14 x 10 mm, ABL Aluminium Components Ltd, GB), two fans (UF3C3-500TC, 12 x 12 x 3 mm, Sunonwealth Electric Machine Industry Co., Ltd., TW), and an NTC thermistor (GAG22K7MCD419, diameter 0.38 mm, temperature range 0 °C to +70 °C, TE Connectivity, CH). When in contact, the tip of the end effector stimulates a circular area on the skin with a diameter of 10 mm.

The voice coil was driven by an audio amplifier (Lepai LP2020A+, Parts Express, USA). The desired vibratory cue (a sinusoidal wave with a frequency of 30 Hz) was generated using the sound card of the PC. For what concerns the TEC module, the desired temperature was guaranteed using a PI controller. A data acquisition (DAQ) system (USB-6218, National Instruments, USA) was used to actuate the Peltier Cell and acquire data from the temperature sensor. Thanks to its tiny dimension, it was possible to place the sensor on the lateral side of the ceramic substrate instead of on the cell surface, making it unobtrusive and imperceptible by the participants during the stimulation. An ad-hoc electronic circuit was in charge of powering the Peltier TEC module and switching the polarity of the supply voltage to reverse the direction of the heat transfer across the two ceramic surfaces, exploiting the Peltier effect. The ceramic substrate of the thermal actuator placed inside the end-effector was arranged in contact with the heatsinks, and the fans were used to flow air inside the ABS

Fig. 3: Upper panels: results of Experiment 1. In a), results showed a statistically significant effect of the type of stimulation (Linear vs Rabbit) on the selected temperature, while the effect of the vibration was not statistically significant. In b), outcomes revealed a statistically significant dependence of perceived pleasantness on type of stimulation and presence of vibration. Lower panels: results of Experiment 2. In c), results showed a statistically significant dependence from the type of stimulation (Linear vs Rabbit) of the selected velocity, while the effect of the vibration was not statistically significant. In d), outcomes revealed a statistically significant dependence of perceived pleasantness on type of stimulation and presence, and no effect for the presence of vibration. The asterisk (*) and (**) indicate the statistical significance $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively.

structure and dissipate the heat generated by the TEC module.

The entire system was controlled by means of a custom software developed in LabVIEW (National Instruments, USA).

B. Experimental Protocol

To investigate the interaction between temperature, vibration, and type of motion to deliver a pleasant stimulus resembling a caress, we used the method of adjustment [29] and asked participants to find the most pleasant sensation by tuning a set of parameters considered meaningful for the stimulus at hand.

Overall, 27 naïve participants took part in two experiments. The sample size was 14 in the first experiment (7 males and 7 females, average age \pm SD: 26.7 ± 3.2), and 13 in the second (6 males and 7 females, average age \pm SD: 28.1 ± 2.9).

By using the customized version of the Omega.3 haptic interface described in Sect. II-A, we generated two types of motion stimuli: a continuous stroke (linear motion stimulus) and a discrete sequence of taps (rabbit stimulus). The two stimuli were applied to the hairy skin of the forearm of the participant (see Fig. 1). In both stimulus types, linear and rabbit, the distance between the starting position and the ending position of the stimulus was 15 cm, while the force applied

by the haptic interface at the contact point was 0.3 N. The two stimuli were presented with and without vibration of the end-effector, and the vibration frequency was set at 30 Hz (in accordance with [25]). As a result, each experimental session consisted of four conditions tested in four blocks: linear without vibration, linear with vibration, rabbit without vibration, and rabbit with vibration. Each condition consisted of 12 trials, of which six trials started the stimulation from the elbow and the other six from the wrist, in random order. A similar experimental procedure was tested in two experiments. In the first experiment, the velocity of the stimulus was fixed and the participant changed the temperature at the contact point, while in the second experiment the velocity was changed by the participants and the temperature fixed. Hence, in each experiment there were four possible trial initial conditions from the combination between two factors: starting temperature (18°C or 42°C) and starting point (wrist side or elbow side) in Experiment 1, and starting velocity (1 cm s^{-1} or 5 cm s^{-1}) and starting point (wrist side or elbow side) in Experiment 2. Each combination was presented three times in random order, for a total of 12 trials per condition, that is 48 trials per experiment. At the end of each trial, participants were asked to rate the

pleasantness of the stimulation on a Visual Analog Scale (VAS) from 1 (low pleasantness) to 10 (high pleasantness).

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

Results are depicted in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b for Experiment 1, and in Fig. 3c and Fig. 3d for Experiment 2. Outcomes pointed out that, among the proposed caress-like stimuli, participants preferred linear movements set at 34.5°C and 3.4 cm s^{-1} . Anyway, a small decrease in the pleasantness ratings was observed for caress-like stimuli provided with discrete sequences of taps at 33.2°C and 2.9 cm s^{-1} . The presence of vibration had a little effect on the pleasantness ratings. These outcomes highlights the significance of selecting optimal parameters for different haptic stimuli to achieve similar perception of pleasantness.

To conclude, our results provide the guidelines to scale down the technological complexity of affective haptics devices without altering the pleasantness of caress-like sensations. The experimental setup we have developed within this study is versatile and adaptable, allowing for the examination of different types of stimuli and their effects on eliciting a wide range of emotions. For instance, future studies can explore different meanings-in-context of touches (e.g., support, affection), diverse gestures (e.g., squeezing, patting), and a broader range of emotions (e.g., anger, fear) to establish a more general protocol allowing effective simplification of haptic signals. Finally, the authors acknowledge that preferred feedback in affective haptics applications is highly subjective. Therefore, the presented findings should consider various factors, including gender, body part, and the interaction of other stimuli (visual/auditory). In future research, we plan to conduct additional studies that specifically focus on exploring differences related to gender and body parts.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Moscatelli, F. M. Nimbi, S. Ciotti, and E. A. Jannini, "Haptic and somesthetic communication in sexual medicine," *Sexual Medicine Reviews*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 267–279, 2021.
- [2] V. Gazzola, M. L. Spezio, J. A. Etzel, F. Castelli, R. Adolphs, and C. Keysers, "Primary somatosensory cortex discriminates affective significance in social touch," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 109, no. 25, pp. E1657–E1666, 2012.
- [3] F. McGlone, J. Wessberg, and H. Olausson, "Discriminative and affective touch: sensing and feeling," *Neuron*, vol. 82, no. 4, pp. 737–755, 2014.
- [4] Å. Vallbo, H. Olausson, and J. Wessberg, "Unmyelinated afferents constitute a second system coding tactile stimuli of the human hairy skin," *Journal of neurophysiology*, vol. 81, no. 6, pp. 2753–2763, 1999.
- [5] R. Ackerley, H. B. Wasling, J. Liljencrantz, H. Olausson, R. D. Johnson, and J. Wessberg, "Human c-tactile afferents are tuned to the temperature of a skin-stroking caress," *Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 2879–2883, 2014.
- [6] H. Olausson, J. Wessberg, F. McGlone, and Å. Vallbo, "The neurophysiology of unmyelinated tactile afferents," *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 185–191, 2010.
- [7] F. McGlone, J. Wessberg, and H. Olausson, "Discriminative and Affective Touch: Sensing and Feeling," *Neuron*, vol. 82, no. 4, pp. 737–755, 2014.
- [8] R. Etzi, C. Carta, and A. Gallace, "Stroking and tapping the skin: behavioral and electrodermal effects," *Experimental brain research*, vol. 236, no. 2, pp. 453–461, 2018.
- [9] G. K. Essick, F. McGlone, C. Dancer, D. Fabricant, Y. Ragin, N. Phillips, T. Jones, and S. Guest, "Quantitative assessment of pleasant touch," *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 192–203, 2010.

- [10] R. Etzi, M. Zampini, G. Juravle, and A. Gallace, "Emotional visual stimuli affect the evaluation of tactile stimuli presented on the arms but not the related electrodermal responses," *Experimental brain research*, vol. 236, no. 12, pp. 3391–3403, 2018.
- [11] L. Bonanni, C. Vaucelle, J. Lieberman, and O. Zuckerman, "Taptap: a haptic wearable for asynchronous distributed touch therapy," in *CHI'06 extended abstracts on Human factors in computing systems*, 2006, pp. 580–585.
- [12] A. Haans, C. de Nood, and W. A. IJsselstein, "Investigating response similarities between real and mediated social touch: a first test," in *CHI'07 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2007, pp. 2405–2410.
- [13] P. Lemmens, F. Crompvoets, D. Brokken, J. Van Den Eerenbeemd, and G.-J. de Vries, "A body-conforming tactile jacket to enrich movie viewing," in *World Haptics 2009-Third Joint EuroHaptics conference and Symposium on Haptic Interfaces for Virtual Environment and Teleoperator Systems*. IEEE, 2009, pp. 7–12.
- [14] G. Huisman and A. Darriba Frederiks, "Towards tactile expressions of emotion through mediated touch," in *CHI'13 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2013, pp. 1575–1580.
- [15] H. Seifi and K. E. Maclean, "A first look at individuals' affective ratings of vibrations," in *2013 World Haptics Conference (WHC)*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 605–610.
- [16] E. Eichhorn, R. Wettach, and E. Hornecker, "A stroking device for spatially separated couples," in *Proceedings of the 10th international conference on Human computer interaction with mobile devices and services*, 2008, pp. 303–306.
- [17] E. Knoop and J. Rossiter, "The tickler: a compliant wearable tactile display for stroking and tickling," in *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2015, pp. 1133–1138.
- [18] T. Moriyama, T. Nakamura, and H. Kajimoto, "Development of a wearable haptic device that presents the haptic sensation corresponding to three fingers on the forearm," in *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM Symposium on Spatial User Interaction*, 2018, pp. 158–162.
- [19] N. D'Aurizio, T. L. Baldi, A. Villani, K. Minamizawa, Y. Tanaka, and D. Prattichizzo, "Wearable haptics for object compliance discrimination through passive touch," in *2021 IEEE World Haptics Conference (WHC)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 894–899.
- [20] C. M. Nunez, B. N. Huerta, A. M. Okamura, and H. Culbertson, "Investigating social haptic illusions for tactile stroking (shifts)," in *2020 IEEE Haptics Symposium (HAPTICS)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 629–636.
- [21] M. Y. Tsalamlal, N. Ouarti, J.-C. Martin, and M. Ammi, "Haptic communication of dimensions of emotions using air jet based tactile stimulation," *Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces*, vol. 9, pp. 69–77, 2015.
- [22] A. Israr and I. Poupyrev, "Tactile brush: drawing on skin with a tactile grid display," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2011, pp. 2019–2028.
- [23] J. Raisamo, R. Raisamo, and V. Surakka, "Comparison of saltation, amplitude modulation, and a hybrid method of vibrotactile stimulation," *IEEE Transactions on Haptics*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 517–521, 2013.
- [24] G. Huisman, A. D. Frederiks, J. B. van Erp, and D. K. Heylen, "Simulating affective touch: Using a vibrotactile array to generate pleasant stroking sensations," in *International Conference on Human Haptic Sensing and Touch Enabled Computer Applications*. Springer, 2016, pp. 240–250.
- [25] A. Israr and F. Abnoui, "Towards pleasant touch: Vibrotactile grids for social touch interactions," *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings*, vol. 2018-April, pp. 1–6, 2018.
- [26] S. Choi and K. J. Kuchenbecker, "Vibrotactile display: Perception, technology, and applications," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 101, no. 9, pp. 2093–2104, 2012.
- [27] H. Culbertson, C. M. Nunez, A. Israr, F. Lau, F. Abnoui, and A. M. Okamura, "A social haptic device to create continuous lateral motion using sequential normal indentation," in *2018 IEEE Haptics Symposium (HAPTICS)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 32–39.
- [28] N. Ferguson, M. E. Cansev, A. Dwivedi, and P. Beckerle, "Design of a wearable haptic device to mediate affective touch with a matrix of linear actuators," in *International Conference on System-Integrated Intelligence*. Springer, 2022, pp. 507–517.
- [29] W. H. Ehrenstein and A. Ehrenstein, "Psychophysical methods," in *Modern techniques in neuroscience research*. Springer, 1999, pp. 1211–1241.